

Table S1. Statistical analysis of factors that has major impact on semen quality subjected to irradiation with Low frequency full duplex (FDX-B) chips.

Total Motility					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
M1	2.767	1	2.767	0.061	0.805
M2	64.261	2	32.131	0.712	0.492
M3	683.226	3	227.742	5.375	0.001*
M4	1457.623	4	364.406	9.393	0.000*
Progressive Motility Score					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
M1	0.064	2	0.032	0.156	0.857
M2	3.98	6	0.442	1.974	0.287
M3	5.12	24	0.213	1.823	0.040*
M4	5.38	46	0.117	3.744	0.004*
Computerised Total Motility					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
M1	15.8	1	15.1	0.880	0.462
M2	103.4	2	17.98	0.964	0.457
M3	11659.2	3	3886.4	97.86	0.001*
M4	11861.7	4	2965.5	76.195	0.001*

To evaluate the effect of all factors affecting semen quality exposed to Low Frequency radio waves, the statistical significance was analysed by linear mixed-effect model followed by PostHoc Tukey Games-Howell test. M1, the effect of treatments on motility; M2, the effect of treatment and time on motility; M3, the effect of treatment on motility, explained with time of exposure and bulls; M4, the effect of treatment on motility, explained by fixed (treatment) and random (time, bull and ejaculate number) effect.

Table S2. Statistical analysis of factors that has major impact on non-return rate in cows during artificial inseminations with semen subjected to irradiation with Low frequency full duplex (FDX-B) chips*.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
M1	0.073	2	0.036	0.355	0.766
M2	1.175	4	0.294	1.004	0.498
M3	0.019	1	0.019	0.064	0.812
M4	1.171	4	0.293	1.589	0.174

*To evaluate the effect of all factors affecting NRR in our system, the statistical significance was analysed by linear mixed-effect model followed by post-hoc Tukey Games-Howell test. M1, the effect of treatments on NRR; M2, the effect of treatment and source of semen (bulls) on NRR; M3, the effect of treatment on NRR, explained with random effect of AI location (technician's effect and site effect); M4, the effect of treatment on NRR, explained with random effect of semen source (bulls) and location of IVF (technician's effect and site effect).

Table S3. Comparison of NRR (56 days) in heifers and multiparous cows AI either with control semen or with semen from the same bulls pre-treated with large FDX-B chip.

a)

Bull		Control			Large FDX-B chip		
		NRR	df	Pearson χ^2	NRR	df	Pearson χ^2
1	Uniparous	79.2	1	<.001	75.5	1	0.019
	Multiparous	75.5			71.4		
2	Uniparous	79.1	1	0.002	75.9	1	0.138
	Multiparous	75.9			75.0		
3	Uniparous	73.5	1	<.001	65.9	1	<.001
	Multiparous	65.9			68.4		
4	Uniparous	84.4	1	<.001	70.0	1	<.001
	Multiparous	70.0			72.3		
5	Uniparous	85.0	1	<.001	73.6	1	<.001
	Multiparous	73.6			73.0		
Total	Uniparous	81.6	1	<.001	71.4	1	<.001
	Multiparous	71.4			71.7		

Table S4.

a) Statistical analysis of factors that has major impact on non-return rate in caws during artificial inseminations with straws containing HF RFID chips*.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
M1	0.118	1	0.118	0.133	0.805
M2	0.611	5	0.122	0.194	0.952
M3	1.143	1	1.143	2.953	0.127
M4	3.160	5	0.632	4.463	0.003*

*To evaluate the effect of all factors affecting NRR in our system, the statistical significance was analysed by linear mixed-effect model followed by post-hoc Tukey Games-Howell test. M1, the effect of treatments on NRR; M2, the effect of treatment and source of semen (bulls) on NRR; M3, the effect of treatment on NRR, explained with random effect of AI location (technician’s effect); M4, the effect of treatment on NRR, explained with random effect of semen source (bulls) and location of AI (technician’s effect).

b) Multinomial logistic regression to identify which factors will affect AI efficiency with straws containing HF RFID chip as compared to control straws.

Final Model: $y = \text{NRR} \sim \text{treatment}$

Effects	Likelihood Ratio Tests				Parameters estimated							
	-2 Log Likelihood of reduced model	χ^2	df	Sig.	β	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(β)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(β)	
											2.5%	97.5%
Intercept	11.004	0	0	.	2.667	0.162	272.588	1	<.001			
Treatment	11.045	0.042	1	0.838	0.046	0.227	0.042	1	0.838	1.047	0.671	1.634

Final Model: $y = \text{NRR} \sim \text{treatment} + \text{Bull} + \text{Technician}$

Effects	Likelihood Ratio Tests				Parameters estimated							
	-2 Log Likelihood of reduced model	χ^2	df	Sig.	β	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(β)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(β) 2.5% 97.5%	
Intercept	136.481	0	0	.	0.002	0.449	0	1	0.996			
Bull	136.654	0.173	1	0.678	-0.031	0.075	0.174	1	0.677	0.969	0.836	1.123
Technician	182.603	46.122	1	<.001	1.618	0.237	46.604	1	<.001	5.041	3.168	8.02
Treatment	138.355	1.874	1	0.171	0.333	0.243	1.876	1	0.171	1.396	0.866	2.249

Figure S1. Total and progressive score motility of semen exposed to low frequency radio waves through Large LF FDX-B chips prior filling the straws.

Figure S2. Power Analysis in “pwr” package in R for sample size estimation for Exp1b (a) and Exp2b (b). Power analysis for logistic regression models for c) Experiment 1b; and d) Experiment 2b, analysed with “WebPower” package in R.